

REPORT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF A MULTIDIMENSIONAL DATA SERVICE IN THE ARTS AND HUMANITIES

AHRC IDAH - SCOPING FUTURE ARTS & HUMANITIES LED RESEARCH

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November 2022

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1. Executive Summary

This report presents results from the AHRC-funded project for scoping a National Data Service to support the creation, archival, analysis, publishing, aggregation and use of multidimensional (2D/3D/4D) data in the arts and humanities. The research was co-developed by an interdisciplinary research team to identify users' needs, relevant initiatives, detailed insight into research and documentation practices as well as ongoing challenges for supporting research in the arts and humanities. Our findings demonstrate the growing interest in deploying multidimensional data within research projects both in Higher Education and Gallery, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAMs) institutions, for instance for documenting objects and environments in collections and archives, heritage science processes and for creative practices. Yet, the potential of the data which is produced remains under-exploited, inaccessible and under-used. Our findings highlight the need to level the playing field for researchers across small, medium and large institutions, democratise access to knowledge and resources, and drive innovation and growth in the UK through novel uses of data. Thus, we propose state-of-the-art infrastructure which addresses user needs to underpin innovative research and institutional practices. Leveraging international initiatives, including interoperability and metadata standards, this infrastructure will lead to a variety of modalities for the aggregation, publication, linkage and re-use of the data. This will enable impact aggregation across and beyond the Arts and Humanities research community.

2. Approach

In this project, which ran from March to July 2022, we aimed to specify a digital data service within the iDAH infrastructure to provide trusted access to, and training in the use of, large and high-quality multi-dimensional (2D/3D/4D) data of cultural heritage and creative works generated through interdisciplinary research. Our research approach has been also interdisciplinary opting for a co-development approach with respect to research processes, activities, analyses and reporting of findings. The research included data collection and analysis through the UKRI Gateway, an online user survey (see Appendix F), case studies for identifying workflows within Arts and Humanities research projects (see Appendix H), a review of 3D archival systems as well as stakeholders' consultation. These activities provided input for the specification and design of the data service which is described in Section B, as well as a business model and work plan for the implementation of the data service (see Section C and Section D). Data was analysed via quantitative and qualitative methods.

Our findings demonstrate that researchers generate in the course of research and institutional projects a mixture of digitised and born-digital data described in 2, 3 and 4 dimensions, including images, 3D objects/environments and time-related media. This data is typically created in non-standardised workflows and stored in personal/institutional storage with little data available for re-use. Our findings also show that the data is complex, multi-format and distributed across files. Hence, requiring careful data management, although metadata/paradata is not standardised for this type of research data. In the Arts and Humanities, researchers often generate large amounts of data (up to 100GB per year) and these are expected to significantly increase in the following years. IPR and content licensing are complex aspects of data handling. Therefore, the research community would benefit from support and clear guidance in this domain.

Overall, smaller organisations are disadvantaged due to a lack of accessing resources and there is a need to promote inclusiveness and democratisation of data technologies. Ensuring the interoperability of the data with international aggregators and data services will allow the UK research community to explore alternative publication modalities and maximise the impact of the research.

Existing solutions for publishing multidimensional data include platforms such as SketchFab (see more details in the review in Appendix E). Although these tools often support the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse) principles to a certain extent, there is a lack of standards to document the creative processes which result in these digital outputs and the frameworks to allow for richer connectivity and interaction with the data. Addressing these shortcomings will enable researchers to unlock the potential of the data by underpinning interdisciplinary collaborations and a range of services to facilitate research, e.g. digital twins, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-assisted analysis.

3. Activities

Table 1 presents the different activities that were developed during the period between March and July 2022. Figure 1 shows the team at the Workshop *Multidimensional Visual Datasets in the Arts and Humanities* which took place on March 29, 2022, at the National Gallery in London UK. The workshop brought together the research team, partners, as well as data producers and users to identify user requirements for a federated data service that addresses the needs of the community.

Activity	What we did?	When?	Who?
UKRI Gateway survey	<i>Surveyed project outputs that include relevant datasets.</i>	February - March 2022	Project Team
Workshops in London and Edinburgh	<i>Consulted with stakeholders about their needs and the proposed service.</i>	29 March and 7 July 2022	~ 70 attendees from HEIs and GLAMs
2-day user needs' workshop	<i>Built capacity on knowledge about 3D repositories, such as MorphoSource.</i>	30-31 March 2022	Project team and partners
Online user survey	<i>Designed, deployed and analysed an online survey for gathering user needs.</i>	March - July 2022	59 responses in AHRC disciplines
Six case studies	<i>Looked into practices for data management and tested MorphoSource.</i>	May - July 2022	6 HEI and GLAM institutions
Outreach	<i>Communication and dissemination activities related to the development of infrastructures for research.</i>	March - July 2022	more than 50 stakeholders

Table 1: Activities developed during the project

As a response to user requirements, the project produces a proposal for a data service, which considers (inter)national initiatives, standards and guidelines for efficient management, preservation and publication of data, while enabling researchers to deploy tools for easy access to the data and tracking for measuring impact and engagement.

Figure 1: Stakeholder Consultation, National Gallery, 29 March 2022

4. Findings and Recommendations

4.1. Multidimensional (2D/3D/4D) data remain unarchived and become inaccessible once the research is completed.

Despite almost 1 in 4 AHRC-funded projects resulting in multidimensional data, its management is not standardised and many researchers lack the skills to manage such data. Small/medium and local/regional institutions remain the most affected by a lack of access to knowledge and resources to deploy multidimensional (2D/3D/4D) data.

Recommendations:

- Novel infrastructure should underpin the curation and management of multidimensional (2D/3D/4D) data, which supports data curation, analysis, publishing, impact measurement, and reuse through a variety of mechanisms, functionalities as well as licensing options.
- The data service should support different tiers of usage to be inclusive and accessible to all levels.

4.2. Multidimensional (2D/3D/4D) data POTENTIAL remains untapped even though it offers innovation opportunities within research and the creative economy.

Multidimensional (2D/3D/4D) data needs to be better linked with a wider knowledge context to support discovery. There is also a need to support richer functionalities to interact with and analyse the data while enabling its measurable impact through a wider range of modalities for publication.

Recommendations:

- The data service should have a common knowledge graph to underpin linking with cross-domain repositories and support aggregation amongst iDAH data services.
- The data service should support novel modalities for publication and interactivity (e.g. immersive environments and digital twins) using on-the-cloud tools/storage, as well as virtual facilities and protocols to interact with large amounts of data.

4.3. Various (inter)national initiatives share challenges for curating and providing access to multidimensional (2D/3D/4D) data.

Compliance with FAIR and CARE principles can be tackled through the adoption of shared standards, charters/principles, software infrastructures and interoperable frameworks, such as IIF-3D all of which depend on joint efforts with other communities.

Recommendations:

- Synergies with other digital infrastructures should be explored to allow for co-developing tools, cross-domain activities, and for providing a platform for UK researchers to reach wider communities.

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Appendix A Background, Aims and Objectives

In this project, which ran from March 2022 to July 2022, we aimed to define the specifications of a digital data service within the iDAH infrastructure which will provide trusted access to, and training in the use of, large and high-quality multidimensional (2D/3D/4D) data of cultural and creative works for research.

This project is part of the AHRC digital research infrastructure programme, which aims to build a national infrastructure for digital innovation and curation for arts and humanities (iDAH). iDAH seeks to unlock the vast and untapped potential of arts and humanities data by establishing a family of interlinked trusted digital repositories that will ensure the data is discoverable, accessible, reproducible, and secure.

Our proposed multidimensional data service specifically addresses the needs of Culture (e.g. GLAM sector, art history, visual arts) and Creative communities, focusing on representational and derivative media created through digitisation processes during research, for instance on cultural collections and archives within the GLAM sector, including their interpretation and conservation, as well as other creative research practices within disciplines such as the visual arts, design, media, and performance. These works often result in large, multi-part, and multi-format datasets which describe the creation process, as in the various steps involved in the digitisation of an artefact into a 3D model, or the project files for their visualisation in an immersive environment or a simulation. Thus, we refer to this content as complex multidimensional data.

The main objectives for developing a data service are to:

1. Make research data compliant with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics) principles.
2. Support open-data and open-science practices when pertinent, including the use of standards, re-use of the data, and reproducibility of the research.
3. Provide extended access to the data via web interfaces, API technology and online data processing services/software.
4. Enable the data's long-term preservation.
5. Support users, including researchers and practitioners, in the production, use, and management of the data.
6. Enable new modalities for the publication and dissemination of research outputs.
7. Underpin new financial sustainability models by enabling the re-use of content by the cultural and creative industries.
8. Guarantee the financial sustainability of the operation of the data service.
9. Innovate in the development and provision of such data services, as well as contribute to the development of standards and technologies in this area to ensure they are cutting-edge.
10. Integrate with other data services to provide a unified infrastructure.

As an outcome, the data service will provide arts and humanities researchers with the resources and capacity to address global challenges and facilitate to unlocking the potential of this data for driving technical innovation (e.g. development of artificial intelligence, and metaverse technologies such as digital twins). The data service will continue to strengthen the position of the UK arts and humanities infrastructure as an international resource, and UK researchers as global players for driving innovation across interdisciplinary research domains as well as within the cultural and creative industries.

Figure 2 illustrates a classification of these datasets according to the following criteria:

- i) **the data creation process**, including complex multidimensional *representational* data produced by digitisation processes, and their derivative-born digital data;
- ii) **the dimensions used to encode the content**, including 2-dimensional, and 3-dimensional datasets as in pixels on an image (x,y) or spatial data/volumetric data (x,y,z) in a 3D scan; and where the 4th dimension is used to represent time or another attribute of the content, as in sensor data, or simulations/visualisations.

Figure 2: Quadrants of Multidimensional Datasets

Appendix B Design Specification for a Multidimensional Data Service in the Arts and Humanities

Our proposal for a trusted data and research service for multidimensional media in Arts and Humanities research includes a distributed infrastructure which is underpinned by the following three pillars:

1. Consortium of members along with a governance/advisory group.
2. Hardware and Software (H/S) distributed infrastructure.
3. Advice and support services for the community of practice.

The following subsections provide details of each of these elements.

B.1 Consortium of members along with a governance/advisory group

The data service will be established first and foremost by its users, who will bring together a community of Arts and Humanities early/mid/late-career researchers and practitioners. There will be a structured governance for the running of the service as well as steering its development. As such, the project will include 1) a management board, formed by the principal investigator, a data service/project manager and members of the implementation board, 2) an implementation board formed by a technical lead, an advocacy lead, a community engagement lead, and a quality control officer, and 3) an advisory board, formed by a selected number of partner institutions.

The PI will have overall responsibility for the development of the project, as well as monitoring and reporting progress, and will be supported by the data service/project manager who will support all tasks related to the management of the project.

The implementation board will have responsibility for the development and operation of the infrastructure on a day-to-day basis. There will be four leads: 1) *Technical Lead* directing the technical decisions on the infrastructure both for software and hardware (see Section B.2), 2) *Advocacy Lead* to ensure the uptake of the data service infrastructure by directing the advice and support services (see Section B.3), 3) *Community Engagement Lead* to reach out to existing and new communities in order to realise the impacts of the project, and 4) *Quality Control Lead* to have oversight of deposition trends

ensure minimum standards are adhered to and categorise deposits by consistent standards (bronze, silver, gold etc).

B.2 Hardware and Software (H/S) distributed infrastructure

Our proposal is for a distributed architecture, with multiple tiers, including a data, application and presentation layer as shown in Figure ??.

The data layer will be implemented through a secure data repository, which will provide access to the data via the application layer. A single data repository will be implemented, based on the MorphoSource platform, at the initial stages of the implementation phase. Thereafter, the project will investigate the potential to integrate alternative institutional repositories for data aggregation. Through this development, we will explore the feasibility of a distributed data layer which can support different workflows and processes within different types of projects across institutions (e.g. art history, conservation, creative practice).

We shortlist a set of components and developments, within the Hardware and Software (H/S) distributed infrastructure:

1. **Data management component** to manage a collection of the media asset with their metadata, inc. the related physical object's information (e.g. artefacts, sculpture, monument, building, exhibition).
2. **Data presentation component** to allow users to search, browse and access information stored in the data service, including media assets and their metadata.
3. **Media viewing component**¹ to easily provide access to media assets supporting different formats and layouts, including 3D meshes, 360 images/videos, CT/MRI, RTI files, point-cloud viewer, Game Engine (e.g. Unity, Unreal) scenes, as well as imaging outputs such as hyper and multi-spectral imaging.
4. **Reporting component** to allow users to create reports on the historical access and usage of the datasets from users for impact purposes, including the number of views, websites linking to the content, number of downloads, number of links pointing to the asset, and google analytics style reporting.
5. **Digital Twin component** to develop and manage a digital twin. Simulation of the digital twin will be out-of-scope for this project but will be explored further as a research element of the project²
6. **REST Application Programming Interface (API) component** to provide extended access to the data via a RESTful Services³.
7. **Virtual Machine (VM) Server** to provide users with Virtual Machines accessing tools with appropriate education/research licenses, such as photogrammetry software, Blender, Meshlab, Unity, Jupyter Notebook, API.

B.3 Advice and support services for the community of practice

This will be developed as a hybrid hub to upskill the community of practice with suitable expertise to create, manage and use multidimensional media. This hub will also be the main mechanism for the exploitation of the data service by proactively communicating, engaging with current and new users and publicising the benefits of the data service.

The hub will 1) organise events and networking opportunities to facilitate communication between the consortium, 2) develop guidelines and white papers, 3) offer training on the use of the data service, as well as 4) offer help and support in the data management life cycle, including:

1. Support the production of a data management plan, which can be used for the proposal submission stage, with a checklist of the main aspects to consider during the project.
2. Identify close-by infrastructure and know-how for training and provision of equipment.
3. Offer resources about recommended workflows, and best practices, including open data and

¹<https://aleph-viewer.com/>

²https://www.iiconsortium.org/pdf/2021_March_JoI_Web_Based_Digital_Twin_SA.pdf

³<https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSDOC6x/REST+API>

open science practices, as well as related literature which will support the decision-making, data acquisition, processing, archival and publishing.

4. Enable the communication between community members through fora and task force groups to work towards standardisations for effective and harmonised complex data management.
5. Provide clear guidance and support through a dedicated tool for assigning copyright and appropriate licences to the datasets. They will be a help point for the interpretation of copyright law.
6. Support FAIR and CARE principles to make data management fair, accessible, interoperable, and reusable while promoting the collective benefit, authority control, responsibility, and ethics for indigenous data governance.
7. Support training opportunities (online, hybrid, face-to-face) to upskill the A&H research community to maximise their potential in multidimensional data acquisition and management without the need to outsource such services when possible. This includes:
 - Training to support copyright and licensing decisions for the community.
 - Training and guidance on how the data can be further deployed for analysis through service functionalities, while highlighting success stories and good practices deployed by sector projects.
8. Enhance the community efforts towards metadata/paradata standardisation by identifying minimum standards for depositing and curating data. This includes the identification and/or extension of ontologies/a knowledge graph to embrace the multidisciplinary of A&H project outputs while employing and extending established vocabularies.
9. Support archiving and curation (storing, metadata, paradata) of born-digital data, which often combine diverse types of data modalities and formats.
10. Showcase examples of data reuse to maximise data deployment and impact.

B.4 Guiding the development: specific requirements

Table 2 list the specific functional requirements for components as identified by our survey of the community (see Appendix F). compliance with FAIR principles and data long-term preservation (see Appendix H), as well as input from the community, gathered via case studies (see Appendix H). Requirements are marked with their priority such as MUST (M), SHOULD (S), and COULD HAVE (C) requirements.

ID	Requirement	Component	Internal ID	Priority
R.1	Add/edit/delete a collection of the media asset with their metadata, inc. the related physical object's information (e.g. artefacts, sculpture, monument, building, exhibition). Support different file formats for the media.	Data management		M
R.2	Specifies clear copyright/license documentation for the published data and the terms of use.	Data management		M
R.3	Ability to add/edit/delete projects, organizations and researchers with attributes including those which support linkages such as ORCID identifiers, DOIs, and ISNI IDs.	Data management	PR09	M

R.4	Provide distinct roles to users (e.g. contributor of data, data curator, data reviewer, data viewer (read-only)) with different permissions and provide secure access to different users/roles to manage information through authentication and rights management.	Data management	PR09	M
R.5	Data maintenance to include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automated conversion of media assets to optimised versions of different resolutions Scheduled testing of media assets resulting in a report to users or appropriate conversion (where possible) to update format versions (e.g. gltf) Data indexing Version control for media assets 	Data management	PR09	M
R.6	Assign a Personal Identifiers (PID) or (Digital Object Identifier) DOI to the media asset to link to reports, publications, and other dissemination channels.	Data management	PR09	M
R.7	Simplified pathways for depositing material by complying with a minimum set of metadata while enforcing referential integrity for individuals and institutions.	Data management	PR09	M
R.8	Consider standardised ontologies, thesaurus and vocabularies, such as PeriodO ⁴ , Geonames ⁵ , World Historical Gazetteer ⁶ , Art & Architecture Thesaurus ⁷ , CIDOC-CRM ⁸ , Dublin Core ⁹ .	Data management	PR09	M
R.9	Performs AI-assisted visual analysis and classification of media assets to support metadata.	Data management		C

⁴<https://perio.do/>

⁵<https://www.geonames.org/>

⁶<https://www.whgazetteer.org/>

⁷<https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/>

⁸<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>

⁹<https://www.dublincore.org/>

R.10	<p>Flexible search interface which provides comprehensive search mechanisms via free text search and faceted search. This should be linked to a variety of criteria linked to the meta-data and paradata including but not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research domain and sub-domain • Data type and format • Modalities of data production • Copyright • Tagging • Depositing body (project, institution, individual) • Usage rights • Collection(s) (to which items belong) • Project(s) (to which items belong) 	Data presentation	PR09	M
R.11	<p>Support rating and tagging mechanisms of media assets. This should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the level of quality (e.g. starts rating), • Identify the level of openness • Identify its suitability for the assets' reuse in various contexts, such as education (e.g. KS1/2/3, HEI). 	Data presentation	PR09	M
R.12	Allow to export and share citation data for a search result or an instance of a media asset.	Data presentation		S
R.13	Allow providing visibility on the 'datasets' contributed by a researcher/organisation	Data presentation		S
R.14	Support for sharing links through social and personal networks.	Data presentation		C
R.15	Support the ability to provide feedback or leave comments on individual media assets, as well as for the publisher to respond to these comments. Moderation tools should allow approved moderators to control the visibility of content.	Data presentation	PR12	C
R.16	Load a 3D scene, with one or more 3D meshes.	View		M

R.17	Load and relight an RTI file which includes a set of relightable images ¹⁰ .	View		M
R.18	Load and allow users to rotate with 3 degrees of freedom on 360 images and videos, including stereoscopic/non-stereoscopic.	View	PR12	M
R.19	Load, view and allow to navigate LIDAR and large scale point clouds ¹¹ .	View	PR12	M
R.20	Load, view and allow to slice CT/MRI data along axes.	View	PR12	M
R.21	Ability to compare naturally aligned image variants, for instance, those obtained by multi-spectral imaging, with a split or curtain viewing functionality ¹² .	View	PR12	M
R.22	Load and allow to save IIF manifests so that it is IIF interoperable.	View		M
R.23	Allow for camera navigation using various modalities, including orbit (e.g., zoom and rotation) and walk-around/first-person navigation.	View	PR10	M
R.24	Have measurement capabilities including length between points, angles between vectors and approximate volumes of the surface.	View	PR12	M
R.25	Ability to create, view and navigate persistent annotations in a structured 3D scene ¹³ . Annotations can be implemented as a link (hyperlink, or Web link) to a Web resource (e.g., a JSON object, an image, a video clip, a sound bite, a program, an HTML document, an element within an HTML document, etc.).	View	PR12	M
R.26	Download high-quality renders (raster images) from the viewer.	View	PR12	M
R.27	Editing the material (e.g. colour, specular, alpha) for a 3D scene.	View	PR12	M
R.28	Editing the scene lighting settings (e.g., light position, direction, colour, intensity, as well as HDR lighting).	View	PR12	M
R.29	Export the current 3D scene as a gltf.	View		M

¹⁰<https://github.com/cnr-isti-vclab/relight> and <https://github.com/cnr-isti-vclab/openlime>

¹¹<https://github.com/potree/potree>

¹²<https://github.com/vanda/curtain-viewer>

¹³<https://taglab.isti.cnr.it/> and <https://github.com/albertbarreiro/TFG>

R.30	Applying a transformation to a 3D scene, inc. Move, Scale, and Rotation	View	PR12	M
R.31	Load, view and allow to navigate Unity/Unreal immersive environments ¹⁴ .	View	PR12	S
R.32	Save the current 3D scene in the database manager.	View		S
R.33	Exploring/adjusting the texture (e.g. multi-texture for physical-based rendering) for a 3D scene.	View	PR12	S
R.34	Editing the scene lighting parameters (e.g., light position, PBR adjustments, HDR lighting).	View	PR12	S
R.35	Support various modalities for rendering primitives of 3D meshes ¹⁵ (e.g., point cloud, wire-frame, transparent, shaded/textured).	View	PR12	S
R.36	Editing the camera parameters, including position, the field of view, lookAt vector and up vector, and allowing for multiple viewports for the 3D scene,	View	PR11/ PR12	S
R.37	Allowing to save pre-set camera views and orthographic views along major axes and isometric perspectives.	View	PR11/ PR12	S
R.38	Ability to provide HTML code to embed a viewer in external sites with customisable elements (e.g. viewer mode, GUI elements).	View	PR09	S
R.39	Animation controls (e.g., start, stop, pause, speed and cycle controls for an animated model) for animated 3D scenes.	View	PR12	S
R.40	AR/VR interaction supports for head-mounted displays (HMD)	View	PR12	S
R.41	Compatibility with a variety of desktop browsers and mobile operation systems, with a year-on-year testing protocol to ensure this is still the case.	View		S
R.42	Integrate accessibility features for the disabled audience for various types of media, such as alternative viewing and audio features by offering 2D visualisations, 360 renders and descriptions of multidimensional datasets.	View	PR12	C

¹⁴<https://needle.tools/>

¹⁵<https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/API/WebGLRenderingContext/drawElements>

R.43	Adapts content to low-bandwidth connections and devices	View	PR12	C
R.44	Allow to create, edit and delete information through POST, PUT and DELETE requests.	REST API		S
R.45	Allow to create, edit and delete information through POST, PUT and DELETE requests.	REST API		M
R.46	Allow to search, query and access media and their metadata using different endpoints to query various types of information, including media assets (e.g. using IIIF-JSON manifests), physical objects, organisations, project equipment, data type, e.g. http://multidataservice.ac.uk/api/media , http://multidataservice.ac.uk/api/physicalobject , http://multidataservice.ac.uk/api/organisation http://multidataservice.ac.uk/api/project It should provide a response in JSON and XML data formats.	REST API		M
R.47	Allow reporting of statistics on access and usage of information in the repository.	REST API		M

Table 2: Prioritised requirements for developing multidimensional data service components

Moreover, Table 3 list the non-functional requirements for the development of the data service.

ID	Requirement	Internal ID	Priority
R.1	Sufficient computing power and storage to run the data management platform as well as components and deal with increasing usage. <i>A starting specification has been suggested of 8 CPU cores, 128 GB RAM, and 400 GB disk.</i>	PR01	M
R.2	Determine the most suitable hosting platform for the infrastructure. An on-the-cloud solution to host the MorphoSource data management platform, as currently, it is not possible to host the MS platform on KCL infrastructure without significant work. Options include Amazon AWS (EU) ¹⁶ , Digital Ocean ¹⁷ or another University infrastructure such as Edinburgh International Data Facility ¹⁸ .	PR04	M

¹⁶<https://aws.amazon.com/>

¹⁷<https://www.digitalocean.com/>

¹⁸<https://www.ed.ac.uk/edinburgh-international-data-facility>

R.3	Develop a Service Level Agreement with 3rd party software provider, in particular for MorphoSource which will be the data management platform.	PR02	M
R.4	Develop a Contributor License Agreement. Following other models, such as Samvera, an agreement should allow for the modification of the software developed by the project, while protecting the IP of all development teams	PR03	M
R.5	Compliance with UK government accessibility standards and EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	KDL01/ KDL02	M

Table 3: Prioritised non-functional requirements for developing multidimensional data service

Appendix C Business plan

C.1 Service proposition

This service capitalises on the high demand for creating and using multidimensional data in research in the Arts and Humanities.

As a unique proposition, we aim to build a trusted, one-stop data service for easily managing, archiving and providing access to multi-dimensional research data, including 2D/3D and 4D datasets, generated through research in the Arts and Humanities. Users will be able to easily manage the data generated during the creation process either via a digitisation workflow or a creative design process. The data will be compliant with the FAIR principles (Findable, Interoperable, Accessible, Reusable) to facilitate its exploitation and CARE principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) to promote communities' participation in data reuse and innovation.

The service will address key needs of researchers and practitioners, in particular:

- Inability to effectively manage multidimensional data as the data management cycle is complex and time-consuming as there is a lack of archival platforms, shared-knowledge on standards, guidelines, preservation and licensing.
- The fact that multidimensional data remains inaccessible, not reusable, and underexploited.
- Inability to track multidimensional data usage which affects the researcher's ability to measure the impact of their research and engage with a wider set of stakeholders.
- Inability to easily share and link multidimensional data as an output of research, including enriching researchers' outputs and CVs.
- The lack of access to training and wider infrastructure, in particular affecting small institutions, to deploy high-quality multidimensional data in research.

As a result, the proposed service for the management of high-quality multidimensional data will unlock the data's innovation potential in research and the creative economy with the following positive consequences benefiting several communities. It will

For **researchers and practitioners**, it will:

- Increase the findability and interoperability of their research outputs.
- Streamline the deposition and ingestion of their research outputs.
- Facilitate experimenting with novel modalities for publication and public engagement with research.
- Improve the high-quality curation and contextualisation of research data.
- Allow for the integration with platforms and institutional repositories, e.g. PURE, and Figshare to improve findability.

For **funders** it will allow efficiently track the outputs of funded projects while ensuring the data access and preservation in the long term. For **research and GLAM Institutions** it will allow for access to research outputs by specialist and non-specialists audiences, fine-grained impact tracking, as well as multifaceted curation of content enabling diverse interpretations. The **creative Industries** will benefit by providing peace of mind when participating in funded projects on the management and preservation of the data produced while allowing them to provide transparent provenance of the data. It will also allow for a wider number of industries to be able to find and reuse research data while having clear copyright associated with it.

Finally, for **developers of other national/institutional infrastructure** it will allow for coordinated national and international efforts in developing infrastructure by leveraging existing international networks which are developing FAIR methods and technologies.

C.2 Funding and marketing strategy

With regards to costs, we identified two types of costs: 1) costs to support building the data service, and 2) costs for ongoing operational costs to cover infrastructure, governance, advocacy and outreach, including the decommissioning the data service.

Funding for building the data service will come mostly from the UKRI-AHRC and co-funded by those institutions involved in its development. Furthermore, the operational costs will be covered by a mixture of revenue streams, including funding from Research England HE Museums fund¹⁹, and revenue from users' fees for using the system.

The current proposal for the fees is a tier system which allows for the deployment of multidimensional data in research by offering free access to several tools as well as support and training. Moreover, for a fee it will be possible to support funded research projects and institutions of various sizes to access a variety of resources. Support for developing the community of practice in the form of training will also mirror this tier system, in which basic support is available for all, while more specialised support and consultancy services will be available for a higher fee. The proposed tiers are as follows:

1. **Basic Plan** (Free)

- Limited amount of storage (e.g. 100GB)
- Restricted levels of access and not possible to mint DOIs
- Access to basic components, inc. data management, viewing and API
- Access to basic tools through a basic VM
- Access to basic support and training
- Preservation of the data

2. **Project Plan**

- A large amount of storage (e.g. 2TB)
- All levels of access and ability to mint DOIs
- Access to basic and advanced components, inc. data management, viewing components, API, reporting, digital twin
- Access to basic and advanced tools through up to 5 VMs
- Access to specialised support and training
- Preservation of the data and perpetual access to the datasets

3. **Institutional Plan**

- Unlimited amount of storage
- All levels of access and ability to mint DOIs
- Access to basic and advanced components, with the possibility to request for updates, changes and customisations
- Access to basic and advanced tools through any number of VMs
- Access to specialised support and training, as well as consultancy services and infrastructure
- Discount for smaller institutions (e.g. 30% discount)
- Preservation of the data and perpetual access to the datasets

C.3 Roadmap

For implementation, we plan a range of engagement and dissemination activities to reach out to stakeholders to ensure the suitability and financial sustainability of the data service. In particular, the community engagement lead and skills/advocacy lead will work together to establish links with the wider community through networking events, training, seminars and demonstrations of the data service. Key collaboration with international efforts, including the IIF-3D technical group, and other repositories such as Europeana and MorphoSource will allow coordination the development of solutions which can benefit the wider international community. The roadmap for the following 3 years is as follows:

1. **Month 1-12:** developmental work will take place during these months (see work plan and justification

¹⁹<https://www.ukri.org/what-we-offer/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/museum-galleries-and-collections-fund/>

of resources for more details).

2. **In month 12:** a prototype service will be available for the community to start using.
3. **Month 12-24:** a fee-based structure for the data service will be identified in collaboration with our advisory board and the community.
4. **Month 24:** a fee-based service will be introduced.
5. **Month 24-36:** the use of the data service based on the fees will be promoted and supported, and the suitability of the fee will be evaluated in months 34-36. Changes will be introduced according to the feedback received.
6. **Month 36:** A fully operational fee-based data service will be available.

Appendix D Workplan

D.1 Work packages

The development of such infrastructure is based on the existing identified user requirements. It will be done through a series of Work Packages (WPs) which will develop the three main pillars of the infrastructure and investigate its economic feasibility.

WP	Activities	Lead
WP1 - Co-design and co-development of data service	1.1 Validating user requirements with user bases, inc. humanities researchers, heritage/natural sciences researchers, GLAM practitioners 1.2 Developing data workflows through small-scale experiments with user bases 1.3 Developing metadata and paradata models and their interoperability with other data services 1.4 Iterative testing and evaluation of components, including usability testing (KDL03), acceptance testing (KDL04), change freeze (KDL05), and security testing (KDL07) 1.5 Review for compliance, inc. accessibility and GDPR (KDL01, KDL02) 1.6 Producing technical and user documentation (KDL09)	KCL
WP2 - Deployment of repository infrastructure	2.1 Design architecture 2.2 Deployment of data repository (MorphoSource) (KDL08) 2.3 Setting up VM servers 2.4 Implementation of API component	Duke, KCL, Edinburgh
WP3 - Development of application components	3.1 Database components 3.2 Viewing components 3.3 Reporting component 3.4 Digital twin-component	KCL, Uo-Brighton, Mnemoscene
WP4 - Implementing community advice and support hub	4.1 Design a structure for community support 4.2 Develop a map of infrastructure 4.3 Consultancy and training 4.4 Copyright advice 4.5 Long-term preservation advice	UWE

WP5 - Dissemination, engagement, exploitation and uptake	<p>5.1 Networking and demonstration events</p> <p>5.2 Website</p> <p>5.3 Business plan</p> <p>5.4 Creation of a Multimodal Data Service organisation</p> <p>5.5 Outreach users and other communities building interoperable technologies and data services</p>	Cambridge
WP6 - Management	<p>6.1 Project management</p> <p>6.2 Advisory Group</p> <p>6.3 Impact and exploitation plan</p>	UoBrighton

Table 4: Work Packages and activities for the implementation of a multidimensional data service

D.2 KPIs

Table 5 lists the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) that the project will focus on for the development stage of establishing the data service.

KPI	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Institutions ingesting datasets	6 institutions	15 institutions	30 institutions
Datasets from AHRC projects	2 projects	10 projects	25 projects
Datasets from other projects	4 projects	10 projects	25 projects
Datasets re-used	50 datasets	200 datasets	300 datasets
Users depositing data in the data service	5 users	50 users	100 users
Users accessing the data service	100 users	1,000 users	5,000 users
Users trained	20 users	50 users	100 users

Table 5: Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for the first 3 years of operation of the data service

Appendix E Review of existing technologies and repositories

Through a review of other repositories for 3D data, we aim to identify existing technologies and gaps in 3D data infrastructure, as well as research capabilities for using and preserving the data.

Champion and Rahaman²⁰ reviewed existing repositories for 3D models, analysing useful features for access, reusability, and preservation.

Our review identified many types of repositories, both public and commercial. These repositories are sometimes established within a project or group/institution to store the data generated by the

²⁰Champion, Erik & Rahaman, Hafizur. (2020). Survey of 3D digital heritage repositories and platforms. *Virtual Archaeology Review*. 11. 1. 10.4995/var.2020.13226.

people within this grouping. In other cases, repositories are established within national and international funding bodies to preserve the data generated by funded projects.

In terms of generic repositories we assessed, Invenio RDM²¹, RSpace²², Zenodo²³ and DataVerse²⁴. These repositories support large-scale research data management and provide support for research outputs. They are often compliant with standards for digital repositories, such as the OAIS reference model which supports the connectivity of the data. However, they do not provide specialised visualisation, linking and access support for multidimensional media.

The International community have developed efforts towards improving access to 3D data for several years now. Examples include the Europeana portal which enables access to 3D data²⁵, the Smithsonian 3D repository which supports their 3D digitisation programme²⁶, and Open Heritage 3D portal²⁷ which makes available the CyArk datasets²⁸. However, these solutions do not support the documentation of the workflows which generated the data, lack support for community standards and interoperability as well as are not easily available to researchers and practitioners.

Repositories which target the management of 3D data resulting from funded research projects include the French National 3D Data Repository²⁹ and the German 3D Repository³⁰ and Kompakkt³¹ which provides the ability to store various types of media, with support for metadata, annotations and for viewing the data.

Other databases of 3D content, although not specific for research, include the popular tool Sketchfab³² and Thingiverse³³ which provides easy-to-use interfaces to distribute 3D data, supporting its commercialisation, as well as support for Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality experiences. These consumer solutions are widely used by UK researchers and the GLAM sector as they allow institutions to disseminate mesh and point cloud models. Whilst Sketchfab has a dedicated cultural data lead facilitating community engagement, the mechanisms for systematically recording metadata are not present, there are no functionalities for data management and analysis, and the platform only supports surface models. Thus, raw photogrammetry datasets and other types of data generated in the creation process are excluded by design.

Our partners, Duke University, have also developed the robust data management platform MorphoSource (<https://www.morphosource.org/>). It is the only platform we know of that explicitly supports most 3D data modalities (including surface-based modalities like structured light and photogrammetry as well as volumetric ones like CT and MRI) with user interface workflows that facilitate good practice. This support includes modality-specific format registries conditioned on user-indicated processing stage, and the ability to connect raw data and successively processed datasets via a data model based on the ISO standard for digital preservation: PREMIS 3.0.

Thus, MorphoSource and our partners, including the IIF-3D community (<https://iif.io/community/groups/3d/>), are part of a growing community building on the well-established interoperable technology and community framework for image delivery for the presentation of 3D data.

These many technologies and efforts demonstrate the level of maturity of the research methods used by the community deploying multidimensional datasets. The literature finding and the features showcased by these technologies confirms our findings. In particular, despite many advances in the preservation of multidimensional datasets, there is still the need for improving the preservation of the data, linking 3D data to larger datasets, improving the advanced visualisation and analytical functionalities, as well as tracking usage of the data.

²¹<https://invenio-software.org/products/rdm/>

²²<https://www.researchspace.com/>

²³<https://zenodo.org/>

²⁴<https://dataverse.org/>

²⁵<https://www.europeana.eu/en>

²⁶<https://3d.si.edu/>

²⁷<https://openheritage3d.org/>

²⁸<https://cyark.org/whoweare/>

²⁹<https://3d.humanities.science/home>

³⁰<https://3d-repository.hs-mainz.de/>

³¹<https://kompakkt.de/home>

³²<https://sketchfab.com/>

³³<https://www.thingiverse.com/>

Appendix F Survey of the community

Through a wider-reaching user survey, we aimed to gather user requirements for specifying further an infrastructure that will address the aims described above. The survey aimed to discover the requirements for a data service from current and future users through a wide-reaching online questionnaire to inform the development of the data service. In particular, we aimed to gather the requirements of the Arts and Humanities community, including researchers and practitioners, to investigate:

- 1) types and quantity of multimodal data, their value, storage arrangements, preservation of data, methods of production and training needs of the researchers generating such datasets, along with the existence of links within national research communication infrastructure;
- 2) users' requirements in terms of application areas (e.g. born-digital complex objects, digital twins, material and digital culture), system features to support 2D, 3D and 4D visual data, visualisation and processing features (e.g. slicing, measuring, interaction), metadata editing and integration/linking/discoverability of data (good practices and FAIR -Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable digital assets- principles).

F.1 Methodology and Sampling

Data was collected through an online survey (Limesurvey platform installed on a GDPR-compliant University server) between June and July 2022. The survey was approved through the formal ethics review process at the University of Brighton.

The survey included both quantitative and qualitative data:

- a) close-ended nominal and ordinal quantitative data to record: participants' information and background in working with complex visual data; types and quantity of multimodal data, their value, storage arrangements, preservation of data, methods of production and training needs of the researchers generating such datasets; users' requirements and future aspirations in terms of application areas, the system features to support for 2D, 3D and 4D visual data, visualisation and processing features (e.g. slicing, measuring, interaction), metadata editing and integration/linking/discoverability of data.
- b) open-ended questions to gather further qualitative insight into participants' opinion about the most appropriate practices, arrangements and functionalities of a Trusted Data Service Repository that addresses the needs of the Arts and Humanities sector, while following FAIR -Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable- principles for digital assets.

Quantitative data was exported from the online survey platform and analysed in Excel for generating suitable visualisations.

We recruited participants through the scoping activity working group network, including the Department of Digital Humanities, King's College London, Digital Humanities Centre, UCL, Art and Design, the University of the West of England, IIF community and consortium³⁴, MorphoSource community as developed by staff at the Duke University, USA and their network. We also recruited participants through JISC mailing lists of the Arts and Humanities research/practitioners community.

F.2 Results

Overall, the survey's findings show that multidimensional data is typically created in non-standardised workflows, researchers lack skills and infrastructure for data management and data is stored mostly in personal/institutional storage with few data being fully published.

F.2.1 Demographics

With regards to the demographics of respondents to the survey, 60% of the survey respondents were residents of the UK. Figure 3-left shows the age distribution of the respondents, with a larger representation (63%) from 25-49 years old respondents. A 52% of respondents identified themselves as males, with a 35% identifying as female (see Figure 3-right). All respondents reported having a Higher Education degree, with experience

³⁴<https://iif.io/community/consortium/members/>

Figure 3: Age range and gender of respondents

Most respondents (82%) had experience in the Arts and Humanities as well as the GLAM sector as shown in Figure 4. Furthermore, a 44% of respondents work as Academics or Higher Education, and 47% work as GLAM professionals or researchers.

Figure 4: Respondents' background

Respondent's involvement in an Arts and Humanities project was varied as many users fulfil more than one role. Most users identified as creators of data (77%), curators of data (74%), with fewer respondents identifying as users of data in subsequent products (45%) as shown in Figure 5-left. As for the purpose, Figure 5-right shows how respondents reported using these datasets mostly for research (89%) and education (55%). Other purposes included enabling public access and public engagement, as well as commercial reasons.

The demographics' responses confirm that we reached the intended profile of users who will readily deploy multidimensional datasets, ranging from early career to established researchers and practitioners in the Arts and Humanities generating and deploying data mostly for research but also for a variety of purposes.

F.2.2 Nature of the data

The community has usually produced complex visual datasets including 2D/3D media through digitisation processes during research on:

- cultural collections and archives within the GLAM sector, including their interpretation and preservation, as well as,
- other creative research practices within disciplines such as the visual arts, design, media, and performance.

Figure 5: Respondents' roles and purposes to work with multidimensional datasets

Respondent surveys confirm our initial insights by showing that these datasets involve a mixture of digitised and born-digital data which can be expressed in 2, 3 and 4-dimensions including time-related media. Often, respondents produce or deploy a large mixture of complex visual dataset types for your research/work purposes through a variety of workflows.

Using the quadrant illustrated in Figure 2, we classified data used by researchers into:

1. Digital surrogate 2D/3D media (*quadrant 1*)
2. Digital surrogate 4D media (*quadrant 2*)
3. Born digital 2D/3D media (*quadrant 3*)
4. Born digital 4D interactive media (*quadrant 4*)

Figure 6 illustrates the use of digital surrogate 2D/3D media (*quadrant 1*), with an 82% of respondents reporting using 2D photographic images as part of their workflows. A further 53% of respondents use 3D meshes, and 12% use 360 photos or videos.

Figure 6: Use of digital surrogate 2D/3D media

Figure 7 illustrates the use of digital surrogate 4D media (*quadrant 2*), with a 39% of respondents reporting using film or video, a 10% using sensor data, and an 8% using motion capture datasets.

Figure 8-left explores further the use of born-digital 2D/3D media (*quadrant 3*), with a 39% of respondents reporting using 3D modelling and animation data, and a 31% reporting using CAD data.

Finally, Figure 8-right presents the use of born-digital 4D media (*quadrant 4*), with a 22% of respon-

Figure 7: Use of digital surrogate 4D media

Figure 8: Use of born-digital 2D/3D media and 4D interactive media

dents reporting using both visualisation and immersive technologies, including Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR).

These responses highlight the need to support at least a variety of data types in the following order of priority:

1. 2D photographic images (82%)
2. Digital surrogate 3D meshes (53%)
3. Born digital 3D models and animations (39%)
4. Film or video (39%)
5. Born digital Computer Aided Design 3D models (31%)
6. Born digital simulation/Visualisations including VR/AR/MR (22%)
7. 360 photos and videos (12%)
8. Sensor data for digital twins (10%)
9. Motion capture datasets (8%)
10. Digital Terrain Model (8%)
11. Imaging beyond the visible spectrum (6%)
12. RTI (6%)
13. CT/MRI (2%)

The above information also indicates the need for the sector to receive support both in terms of infrastructure and training to leverage the potential of combining multiple types of data, and exploring additional data modalities for research.

With regards to workflows, these vary widely with many users deploying photogrammetry processes to generate digital surrogate 3D meshes using a variety of 3D cameras. The use of 3D scanning and

LIDAR equipment, including on mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets is also mentioned. Other scientific instruments, such as X-Ray, multi/hyperspectral cameras and 3D geophysical analysis are also reported with a variety of image files produced. A variety of cameras are also used to produce film and video; as well as sensors for generating datasets such as body movement, or other environmental data. Moreover, CAD tools and 3D modelling tools, such as 3D Studio Max and Blender, are also used for generating assets and post-processing 3D meshes. Game Engines, such as Unity and Unreal, for developing born digital visualisation and simulations are also commonly used. This often includes workflows which include design, importing 3D assets, lighting, and programming.

The volume of data often generated through these workflows is often hard to establish. We asked respondents to give an average of the data they might deploy yearly, acknowledging that this is not a constant year-on-year. Unsurprisingly, respondents often don't know how much data they generate (22%), but a large amount (45%) reported generating between 1 and 100 GB per year as shown in Figure 9-left. This volume was expected to increase significantly in the future by a 56% of the respondents (Figure 9-right).

Figure 9: Average volume of data generated in a year by researchers and expectations for this volume of data to increase

Figure 10 illustrates the most popular solutions for storing the datasets generated by respondents, including institutional repositories (33%), but also many respondents reported using personal storage (e.g. hard drives) (29%) and institutional data storage (e.g. OneDrive) (29%).

Figure 10: Storage arrangements for existing datasets

Figure 11 illustrates that a large majority of respondents (70%) make available their data through

existing online platforms, such as Sketchfab and Europeana, as well as through project websites.

Figure 11: Method of access to existing datasets

Respondents also reported using domain-specific archiving solutions, including the Archaeological Data Service (<https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/>), Morphosource (<https://www.morphosource.org/>), Figshare (<https://figshare.com/>), OpenTopography (<https://www.opentopography.org/>), OpenHeritage3D (<https://openheritage3d.org/>).

With regards to specific features or functionalities which influence user's decision choice of platform for storage and access, these often include with no order of preference:

- Ease of use and ability to embed results
- Ability to access present data through the web
- Low cost/Free usage and storage
- Possibility to connect the 3D data with the research data behind it
- Platforms' reach and audience
- Long-term archiving and preservation
- Control level of access
- Integrations with 3rd party software
- Support for researchers, including training
- Platform's institutional policy
- Control over IP, level of access, and security of data

When asking about the IPR for the datasets generated, often researchers use the Creative Commons family of licenses (47%), although, 20% of respondents do not usually get involved in assigning these rights (Figure 12-top). Regarding specific Creative Commons (CC) licenses used, respondents reported a mixture of licenses, with popular options being CC BY-NC, and CC-BY (see Figure 12-bottom).

F.2.3 Features required from a data service

The survey asked respondents to let us know how important certain features to interact with multidimensional datasets were for them. To understand how these features supported users to interact with data, we classified features under four categories:

Figure 12: IPR licenses for datasets and common type of Creative Common licenses commonly for datasets

1. The software features required when interacting with a SINGLE asset, (usually a 3D dataset).
2. The software features required when interacting with MORE THAN ONE asset.
3. The software features required when interacting with a LARGE AMOUNT of assets.
4. The software features required when controlling access to assets.

Respondents rated various features for interacting with a single 3D asset, including those to enable viewing and editing the 3D asset (see Figure 13). There are many 3D viewers available in the market, including the viewer on the SketchFab site, which has such functionalities by default. With regards to more than one asset (see Figure 14), respondents asked for the ability to interact with various assets through a 3D scene, and side-by-side for comparison. These include the following features as extremely important or very important:

1. Viewport navigation using various modalities (e.g., zoom and rotation, walk around) (88%)
2. Annotating the asset (67%)
3. Measurement capabilities (67%)
4. Downloading rendered screenshots (57%)
5. Editing the asset (e.g., slicing, scaling, removing or adding parts, transforming/posing models) (53%)
6. Side-by-side viewing of multi-channel imagery (e.g., curtain viewers) with synchronisation of navi-

Figure 13: Responses for software features required when interacting with a SINGLE asset

gation controls (53%)

7. Supporting various modalities for visualising assets (e.g., point cloud, wireframe, texture, theatre/VR/AR viewing) (51%)
8. Editing the material and/or texture (e.g., materials' inspection, UV parameters) (51%)
9. Assembling a scene bringing different assets together (47%)
10. Editing the scene lighting parameters (e.g., light position, PBR adjustments, HDR lighting) (45%)
11. Editing the scene camera parameters (e.g., the field of view, allowing multiple viewports, full screen) (37%)
12. Orthographic viewing option (non-perspectival, useful for schematic perspectives when combined with transparent view and wireframe) (35%)
13. Basic animation features (e.g., playback, speed and cycle controls for an animated model) (24%)

Furthermore, respondents requested the ability to interact and manipulate many assets mostly via an API which offers functionalities for search, query and access as extremely and very important (75%). The API should allow for various types of users, and levels of secure access. It will also be useful to allow for batch uploading and editing of the assets including their metadata. This could allow for a wide variety of operations on a large number of assets, including deploying algorithms to analyse and enrich the assets with additional information.

As Figure 15 illustrates, other functionalities which allow users to bring together, up to a large amount of, related assets. This includes the ability to create reports on the access and usage of the datasets from users for impact purposes (55%), create and manage a digital twin (35%) and access to notebook functionalities for implementing algorithms on the data (e.g., machine learning algorithms in tools such as GoogleColab).

Lastly, respondents were asked to provide input on those features which support sharing, accessing and using datasets widely both by creators and users. Figure 16 shows preferences from respondents, which prioritised allowing the content to be interoperable via IIIF, supporting extended metadata and paradata, providing code to embed a viewer in other HTML pages with customisable elements (e.g. viewer mode, GUI elements), adapts to low-bandwidth viewers, support rating, feedback and tagging mechanisms.

Other functionalities requested included the ability to access multiple resolution versions of 3D assets, the ability to easily create digital narratives (e.g. 'scrollytelling'), the ability to easily transfer datasets to other platforms to reach different audiences, the ability to flag content for easy re-use in other contexts,

Figure 14: Responses for software features required when interacting with MORE THAN ONE asset

support to share in social media, and integrations for non-expert users to IIIF functionality to easily access and pull digital objects into other IIIF viewers/applications.

F.2.4 Training needs

To understand how a data service can support to develop a community of practice with suitable expertise to create, manage and use multidimensional data, we asked a set of questions to get feedback on current training and future needs.

A 71% of respondents reported having never received any training to produce or deploy complex visual datasets for their research/work purposes. For those who are trained, many of these activities are self or informal learning activities. Very few formal learning activities, for instance, as part of degree courses, are reported.

With regards to barriers to developing or deploying multidimensional datasets, respondents reported budget or time being a major barrier (78%), followed by a lack of access to technical infrastructure (69%) and lack of knowledge and training (67%) as shown in Figure 17.

Moreover, when asked about the main aspects of developing, deploying and managing complex visual datasets that they would need the most training or support with, respondents highlighted various areas. As top priorities (see Figure 18), respondents highlighted the need for more support on the data management cycle, such as documentation through metadata and paradata (41%), providing suitable access to and interaction with datasets (47%), best practices for preservation (57%), and aggregation of datasets inc. linking datasets to other resources (59%). Although with less priority, respondents also requested support to process (37%) and create datasets using various equipment and instruments (35%).

Further to the need for training on soft skills, access to hardware and software for digitisation and processing of datasets was also identified (see Figure 19). Respondents reported the need for on-the-cloud storage (67%), instrumentation (61%), such as 3D scanners, cameras in and beyond the visible spectrum, and motion capture facilities, as well as supercomputer facilities for processing data (53%). Others also highlighted the need for access to consultancy services and know-how to support projects (53%).

The need for training was further reinforced when investigating how the data service could support creating and monitoring the usage of high-quality open data. 54% of respondents favour the support

Figure 15: Responses for software features required when interacting with a LARGE AMOUNT of assets

by training developers and users, as well as providing documentation about the use of the data service (22%) and highlighting high-quality open data datasets (12%) as shown in Figure 20-left.

Requirements for supporting open-data and open-science practices when pertinent was also investigated, including the use of standards, re-use of the data, reproducibility of the research, and the need for open-science support. As Figure 20-right illustrates, the relevance of the FAIR principles towards promoting open data and science practices was also highlighted, and this is further discussed in the next Section of this report. The development of a community of practice (10%), sharing cases and projects (8%), and supporting institutions to adopt open data practices (21%) were also seen as important enablers.

Finally, concerning open data, respondents highlighted the need for further support in clearing the intellectual property. For instance, having clarity with regards to the copyright protection for 3D datasets out of copyright works.

F.2.5 Publication modalities and business models

We also explored how such data service could underpin new publication modalities for researchers, beyond traditional, academic publications, while allowing for financial sustainability models by enabling the re-use of content by the cultural and creative industries. When asking about the features which will be useful to support the publication of multidimensional dataset as research outputs of their own, 94% of respondents agreed that the ability to assign a DOI to link to reports, publications and other dissemination channels were required (see Figure 21). Others also responded that it would be useful to have the ability to export citation data for the media asset(s) or cite shareable viewers (69%), and the ability to link to ORCID (61%).

Furthermore, 55% of respondents were interested to license the content to external parties and industry to explore new business models. Although 41% were not interested in exploring further this (see Figure 22-left). A further 25% mentioned interest in interacting with NFT services and crowdfunding projects through the data service.

Finally, when investigating the financial sustainability of such data service, respondents preferred in order of priority to pay by a project-specific payment (39%), having a free service (25%), as well as by a tier system (24%) as shown in Figure 22-right. A good strategy will be to have a tier-based framework which allows a small number of projects, size of data, levels of access, followed by a more comprehensive set of packages for the following tiers.

Figure 16: Responses for software features required to allow users to share, access and use datasets to assets

Figure 17: Issues encountered when deploying multidimensional datasets

Figure 18: Main aspects to consider for training

Figure 19: Infrastructure which will benefit the research community alongside the data service

Figure 20: Responses for supporting to create and monitoring the usage of high-quality data and for enabling open data and science practices

Figure 21: Respondents' opinions on useful features to support the publication of complex visual datasets as research outputs on their own

Figure 22: Mechanism by which respondents are willing to experiment with new business models on the content created and by which respondents' institutions will be willing to pay for a data service

Appendix G Compliance with FAIR principles and long-term preservation

To underpin the exploitation of the data for a variety of purposes, data services must address requirements for making the data compliant with the FAIR principles. This involves making the data to be findable (F), accessible (A), interoperable (I) and re-usable (R), and requires addressing the following requirements:

- Findable content:
 - Media assets should be assigned DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers).
 - Media should be described with rich metadata to document their creation and processing according to domain recommendations.
 - Media assets should allow for easy linking to other assets in external repositories
 - Media assets should be indexed and catalogued to allow for effectively browsing and searching for data
- Accessible content:
 - Media assets should be retrievable by their DOI using a standardised communications protocol (open, free, universal, allowing authentication and authorisation). This is a must: Support DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers)
 - Media assets should be accessible, even when the data are no longer available
- Interoperable content:
 - Media assets should use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
 - Media assets should use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
 - Media assets should include qualified references to other (meta)data
- Reusable content:
 - Media assets should be richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes, including clear and accessible data licences, data provenance, and community standards.

Different options for describing metadata and paradata which can support these requirements identified by the community in our user survey include Dublin Core³⁵ and CIDOC-CRM³⁶. Moreover, CIDOC-CRM contains suitable modelling entities to describe the steps and methods for the production of media assets such as those proposed by this data service³⁷.

Furthermore, to address the data's long-term preservation, there are various guidelines from the Digital Preservation coalition³⁸. Most notably, there is specific advice for researchers to follow the best practises for preservation, including the consideration of IPR and licensing of assets³⁹. With regards to the data service infrastructure requirements, it is important to consider access to assets that might be not-easily accessible or outdated, including:

- Compatibility to access assets in a variety of desktop browsers and mobile operating systems, with a year-on-year testing protocol to ensure this is still the case.
- Supporting a variety of formats as well as conversion amongst formats, with specific advice on the best formats for forward compatibility.
- Accessibility features to access various types of media

³⁵<https://www.dublincore.org/>

³⁶<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>

³⁷<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmdig/>

³⁸<https://www.dpconline.org/docs/technology-watch-reports/2479-preserving-3d/file>

³⁹https://www.zotero.org/groups/4614642/complex_3d_data_repository_scoping/collections/GUWGJUWJ/items/KRUV489I/item-list, https://zenodo.org/record/6242611#.YqG_SOzMJhG, <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/3d-digitisation-and-intellectual-property-rights>

Appendix H Case studies illustrating the production, management and access of cultural and creative works

The research sought to gather additional requirements by collecting information on complex visual data generation and management by several institutions and by testing a MorphoSource prototype for evaluation. The prototype was deployed in the Kings Digital Lab. To gather information from a broad set of organisations working with 3D datasets within the A&H research context, a case study approach was employed. Hence, we reached diverse types of institutions, including academia, the GLAM sector, and practitioners, to gather a wide variety of data.

A phased investigation approach was put in place including feasibility evaluation through the collection of data and a series of interviews with the custodians of data.

Therefore, for each case study, the initial aim of the research team was to understand the feasibility of accessing and using datasets for further investigation. This involved deploying a set of first-level questions which broadly investigated issues such as data type, custodianship, data provenance, metadata, and copyright for each project. All information was gathered through a case study candidate form with questions and based on the provided information a subset of case studies was selected to explore at a more detailed level.

Following the feasibility stage, and after refining the subset of the case studies, a series of individual interviews took place with the custodians of the datasets to discuss more in-depth issues on data management for each project/dataset. Such investigation topics include, precise data storage arrangements, metadata and paradata related to the datasets, access to data by broader research audiences, deployment of data for a variety of research-related purposes (documentation, preservation and dissemination of A&H information), digitisation methodologies and workflows as well as formats and skills involved in generating data and research outcomes.

The third research phase for the case studies revolved around testing the provided datasets to examine in-depth how this could be ingested and managed through a data service and repository using the MorphoSource prototype.

The following sections present a summary of the case studies in terms of project type, the context for data generation and handling and available data types for testing.

H.1 Dispersed collections for research - Darwin 3D (University of Cambridge)

- **Project:** Darwin 3D
- **Context:** This case study illustrates the need to bring together, and recontextualise the digital surrogates of Charles Darwin's collected specimens, records (correspondence) and other materials which now belong to dispersed collections and archives in various Cambridge organisations including Cambridge Digital Library, Cambridge University Herbarium, Museum of Zoology, Sedgwick Museum of Earth Sciences, The Fitzwilliam Museum, Whipple Museum of the History of Science. The project is a proof-of-concept to link collections and engage audiences with Darwin's work by complementing selected correspondence (Darwin wrote to 2000 people throughout his life and his work includes more than 12000 letters and articles) with 2D/3D visualisations of specimens, equipment and objects that relate to his work (see example in Figure 23). The exhibition Darwin in Conversation⁴⁰ is the output of this work (initially in Cambridge and in 2023 in New York) as well as an event in Cambridge in October 2022 to release all visualisations via various platforms through QR codes etc particularly targeting young audiences.
- **Workflows:** CT scans for the zoological and botanical material (Nikon Micro CT scans); Photogrammetry for the external acquisition of specimen and objects; RTI for some of them. 3D models through photogrammetry is stored on SketchFab and CT scans on Morphosource. RTI is still a work in progress. The material will be available through Cambridge's Digital Library platform and SketchFab will be used as a backend for 3D models and Morphosource as a backend for the CT scans. The research team are looking at options for the RTI. The material from SketchFab will be copied in Morphosource as well as a point.

⁴⁰<https://www.darwinproject.ac.uk/darwin-conversation-exhibition>

- **Data types:**
 - Digital Surrogates: 3D meshes via photogrammetry (Canon DSLR synced via laptop/software to turntable, Reality Capture), Nikon Micro CT scans
- **Services:** Archiving, publishing/engagement
- **Data storage:** Institutional storage, Morphosource, Sketchfab
- **Copyright:** Cambridge Digital Library
- **Deployed licenses:** CC BY, CC BY NC

Figure 23: Auxanometer model, by the Cambridge Digital Library on SketchFab under CC BY NC

H.2 Music collections with immersive scenes - Space, Place, Sound and Memory (University of Edinburgh)

- **Project:** Space, Place, Sound and Memory, AHRC-funded project
- **Context:** This was an interdisciplinary project led by the The University of Edinburgh in collaboration with external partners. The project's scope was to bring closer performance practice, gaming and virtual reality (VR), technology, as well as heritage sites with particular historic significance. The project's team deployed 3D imaging, binaural and surround sound, and room-impulse responses to create a software application which enabled users to experience an Early Music concert in the historic space of Linlithgow palace and St Cecilia's Concert Hall in Edinburgh (see Figure 24).
- **Workflows:** The sites had been LIDAR scanned by the Historic Environment Scotland (who hold the copyright of raw files) and then meshes were edited by the team at the University of Edinburgh (holds the copyright of edited meshes). An external partner was responsible for the audio recordings etc. Scanner data were converted into meshes and then they were pooled into 3DS Max and Blender to reconstruct the spaces or used to reconstruct the original spaces. Datasets were then pulled into Unity and Unreal and real-time acoustic retracing software was used to generate the profiles. These profiles were used to produce the audio and the models were used to generate the interactive experiences and the audio was pulled into those once generated.
- **Data types:**
 - Digital Surrogates: LIDAR scan data, point clouds, 3D meshes, 2D images, audio files, 360 photos
 - Born digital data: Unity and Unreal engine Project Files, VR Application, 2D renders video files
- **Services:** Archiving, publishing/engagement
- **Data storage:** Institutional storage, private storage
- **Copyright:** University of Edinburgh, Hyperion, Historic Environment Scotland
- **Deployed licenses:** CC BY NC

Figure 24: St. Cecilia immersive experience by the University of Edinburgh, under CC BY NC

H.3 Listed site data to facilitate site management and potential audience engagement - Roman Baths (King's College London)

- **Project:** Roman Baths at King's College London
- **Context:** The Roman Baths at the King's College London are a network of rooms below the Surrey Street buildings on the premises of the KCL. The site is listed at Grade II as a rare example of Jacobean cistern providing archaeological evidence for the Old Somerset House gardens as well as illuminating the commercial development of bath houses in the 18th century. The purpose of the the project was to reconstruct the Baths' original appearance via 3D modelling (see Figure 25) and to capture its current state through digitisation to document sites on campus. Another future goal is to disseminate information and enhance the appreciation of the site as the Baths do not constitute a well-known site of urban environmental history and hence are not much visited by the public.
- **Workflows:** A model of the baths was generated by a Digital Humanities student in 2013 in 3DS Max and then in 2015 another model was outsourced and was produced in 3DS Max by a private company. Another acquisition was done with a FARO scanner and this was outsourced.
- **Data types:**
 - Digital Surrogates: scan data, point clouds, 3D meshes, 2D images
 - Born digital data: 3D modelling data, 2D renders
- **Services:** Archiving, publishing/engagement, site management
- **Data storage:** Institutional storage, private storage, SketchFab
- **Copyright:** King's College London, National Trust
- **Deployed licenses:** - CC BY NC

H.4 Listed church site data to enhance site management and for audience engagement - St Mary Le Strand (King's College London)

- **Project:** St Mary Le Strand at King's College London
- **Context:** St Mary Le Strand is located on the premises of the King's College London and constitutes a listed building under the Planning Act 1990 due to its special architectural and historic interest. The church received resilience funding in 2021 from the National Lottery Heritage Fund and part of this funding was used to update and deploy 3D visualisations of the church on its website to enhance audience engagement (see Figure 26). The church in its original state, as designed and built by

Figure 25: Roman Baths point cloud by the KCL on Sketchfab

architect James Gibbs, as well as in its current the state can be visited online through a virtual visit⁴¹. The creation of 3D data for this project is twofold as it also aims at generating a proposed model for the deployment of the church to host art events while keeping its character as a place of worship.

- **Workflows:** Models generated through 3D design software SketchUp by a private architecture firm which was employed by the Parochial Church: three versions (original church by James Gibbs, current state, a proposal for deployment as an arts events venue). Also, BIM data are available from the same company (rvt format). There has also been done a LIDAR scan acquisition of data by another private company, yet the company would only share data at an extra cost.
- **Data types:**
 - Digital Surrogates: LIDAR scan data (not accessible to the team as they were created by an external company)
 - Born digital data: 3D modelling data, BIM data
- **Services:** Archiving, publishing/engagement, site management
- **Data storage:** Institutional storage, private storage
- **Copyright:** Parochial Church Council of the Ecclesiastical Parish of St Mary le Strand & St Clement Danes
- **Deployed licenses:** - CC BY NC ND

H.5 3D imaging and digital fabrication for conservation and presentation of paintings - The Harbour by Archibald Peddie (University of West England Bristol)

- **Project:** The Harbour by Archibald Peddie at UWE Bristol (AHRC Collaborative Doctoral Award)
- **Context:** This was an AHRC Collaborative Doctoral Award to explore the potential of 2.5D and 3D imaging to acquire texture and shape information from paintings for conservation, presentation and audience engagement purposes. The research explored practical workflows for the generation of high-quality 3D replicas of cultural heritage objects and their applications to the scientific documentation of artworks, online engagement and tactile reproductions. For the research the painting 'The Harbour' by the Scottish artist Archibald Peddie was deployed -amongst others- to test complex data acquisition, workflows and generation of digital and physical outputs through 3D printing (see Figure 27).
- **Workflows:** Different workflows were deployed, e.g. a workflow to laser scan (Lucida scanner) and then merge laser scan data with RTI (extensive work in image processing and registration); a workflow to merge photogrammetry data with RTI (extensive processing of photogrammetry data

⁴¹<https://stmarylestrand.com/virtual-heritage-visit/>

Figure 26: St Mary le Strand by the Parochial Church Council of the Ecclesiastical Parish of St Mary le Strand & St Clement Danes on the church's website

and data optimisation); decimated model uploaded to SketchFab; video animation done in Blender to show model; experimentation developing a surface scanner. In the past mostly merging laser scan data with RTI, now mostly photogrammetry data with RTI. Experimentation with 3D printing as well.

- **Data types:**

- Digital Surrogates: scan data, point clouds, 3D meshes, 2D images, RTI images
- Born digital data: 2D renders, video files

- **Services:** Archiving, publishing/engagement

- **Data storage:** Institutional storage, private storage, SketchFab

- **Copyright:** -

- **Deployed licenses:** -

Figure 27: The Harbour by Archibald Peattie, by the UWE on SketchFab 3D model and normal map of the painting by UWE

H.6 3D digitisation of collection for research and audience engagement - Chinese Oracle Bones (British Library)

- **Project:** Chinese Oracle Bones at the British Library

- **Context:** A small collection of 3D models of Chinese oracle bones which form part of a wider collection of 480 oracle bones from the British Library. In the 2015 UK-China Year of Cultural Exchange, the

British Library received funding from the Department of Culture, Media and Sport to develop and strengthen its links with the Chinese institutions, and to deliver a project based on cooperation and mutual exchange. The collection of bones was digitised in 2D and a sample of five models were produced through photogrammetry and 3D printing (see Figure 28). Oracle bones were animal bones, usually ox shoulder bones or the the underside of turtle shells, used for divination rituals in ancient China. Dating to the Shang dynasty (c. 1600 – 1050 BC), they bear the earliest extant form of Chinese writing and are the oldest items held in the British Library.

- **Workflows:** In the British Library, collection items imaging is done by Imaging Services; the photographs are then sent to a private company which creates the 3D models and uploads them to Sketchfab (with a basic description). Metadata for Sketchfab is created by the curator and/or digital curator of the BL and added to the models. Metadata for the BL repository is created by the digital curator and the Repository Service Lead. The private company/external collaborator sends the BL the files they have produced (TIFF, the 3D models in both GLB and glTF formats alongside the JSON files) for preservation purposes. As of 2018, Imaging Services do the acquisition of collection items using a 3D photography rig composed of a set of cameras and a turntable. For the Chinese Oracle Bones collection, the setup was simpler with the studio equipment and a turntable that was purchased for this reason. Production of these 3D models was done by the digital curator.
- **Data types:**
 - Digital Surrogates: 2D images, 3D meshes via photogrammetry
- **Services:** Archiving, publishing/engagement
- **Data storage:** Institutional storage, SketchFab
- **Copyright:** No copyright associated with the 3D models
- **Deployed licenses:** CC BY

Figure 28: Chinese oracle bone by the British Library on SketchFab and the British Library website under CC BY

H.7 Case studies' findings

This section presents the main findings from the case studies that we deployed for the research. The findings from the case studies were coded and analysed based on the data management lifecycle/plan classification in order to develop a deeper understanding of the Arts and Humanities community's requirements with respect to managing complex datasets. This data management life cycle is based on existing guidance⁴² for managing multidimensional datasets. Figure 29 illustrates these steps, which

⁴²https://www.ala.org/acrl/sites/ala.org.acrl/files/content/publications/booksanddigitalresources/digital/9780838939147_3D_OA.pdf

start from the planning for data acquisition and describe the creation, processing and archival of a multidimensional dataset. Further analysis of the data, as well as publication and use-reusing of the resulting data is also represented in the cycle.

Figure 29: Multidimensional data management lifecycle

Thus, the main findings of the case studies are presented below according to these steps.

H.7.1 Data planning

There have been many efforts, referred to by respondents as proofs-of-concept, by the A&H research community to produce, deploy, combine 3D data with other assets for various purposes including research, audience engagement and awareness etc. Researchers and institutions experiment with different data management plans, depending on resources (e.g. skills, funding). However, often funding is limited to plan for 3D data acquisition. Sometimes, research funding is supplemented internally by institutions to support 3D data generation with a specific purpose which is of strategic relevance to the institution (e.g. conservation, audience engagement).

The main finding in this area is that data planning is closely related to the budget. Smaller organisations are often disadvantaged due to a lack of resources when it comes to data creation and data management. Further support to researchers in these institutions will ensure that researchers across the sector are creating high-quality data and managing this to support use, re-use and long-term preservation.

H.7.2 Data creation and processing

When undertaking data creation, the community deploys different workflows for digitisation, archiving of the data generated by these processes, and publishing. Often, post-production documentation is overlooked even though it is a laborious essential phase in the data lifecycle. There is also no sufficient consideration for documenting born-digital data.

Hence, information on the steps taken to produce data often becomes lost as there is no provision for holistic data management to record and store processing data stages. There are lots of proprietary

files which are generated during data processing, and these are often lost or not kept even though they include valuable information about the different data workflow stages. When proprietary files are kept, there might not be accessible to them due to expensive software licenses.

Moreover, often data creation is outsourced due to a lack of equipment, lack of skills/knowledge and other resource-related obstacles. When data generation is outsourced, there might be limited access to files (often at extra cost) due to unclear copyright state.

Overall, researchers need support to effectively perform data management, as well as support for easy recording of the creation and processing stages of the data. Further advice would also benefit researchers, with regard to licensing content from external companies who might be undertaking the digitisation.

H.7.3 Data curation, archiving and preservation

A great volume of data is stored in private/personal drives or institutional repositories. Data often needs to be converted into different formats to comply with different repositories, sometimes losing quality when undertaking these conversion processes. The lists below present a sample of data file formats from the case studies which were deployed for the research of the scoping activity.

Digital Surrogates:

- 2D photographic images: *Canon RAW CR2, TIFF, JPG, PNG, PSB, RAW, PSD*
- 3D digitisation mesh and point clouds (e.g., photogrammetry, 3D scans, optical microscopy): *OBJ, MTL, Agisoft PSX, GLB, GIFT, blend, PTS, PLY, LSPROJ*
- Digital Terrain Model (TIN / LiDAR etc.)
- Imaging beyond the visible spectrum (e.g., Multispectral/Hyperspectral/Infrared/X-ray)
- Computed tomography (CT) /Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) data: *DICOM*
- Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI): *PNG and PTM*
- 360 Photos and Video
- Video or Film
- Motion capture datasets
- Sensor data (e.g., for Digital Twins)
- Audio: *WAV*

Born digital data:

- Computer-Aided Design (CAD) data: *DWG*
- 3D modelling/sculpting and animations: *MAX, SKP*
- Simulations/Visualisations creative content: *MOV, MP4, JPG*
- Immersive environments (VR/AR/MR): *EXE, PAK, UMAP, UPROJECT*

Other formats: *RIS, PDF, LOG, XML, DOC, DOCX, TMP, JSON, INI, TXT, EXE, VERSION, RES, CFU, ICU, BRK, TPS, TTF, HLSL, GLSL, DLL, SO, APK, BAT, LIB, EXP, PDB, TARGET, UASSET, PHONONSCENE, BAKEDSCENE, DDC, BIN, DEPS, DAT, PCH, CS, CPP, UPLUGINMANIFEST, H, DMP, CPP*

There is a need for more efficient collaborative environments as well as flexibility to archive and curate data especially for projects with several partner institutions, where distinct parts of the data archiving and curation might be undertaken by different researchers.

Readily available platforms, such as SketchFab, are often deployed by institutions for audience engagement, yet the focus is on publishing rather than archiving or preserving the data, as well as supporting discoverability to cover the wide spectrum of arts and humanities research.

Currently, there is a variety of metadata and paradata models for recording multidimensional data. Hence, the community needs better coordination in the standards, ontologies and vocabularies deployed to improve findability.

H.7.4 Data analysis

Few researchers perform further analysis on the data generated beyond experimenting with its visualisation by a variety of users, for instance, when generating an immersive interactive VR/AR experience. This might highlight the need to upskill the research community in a variety of analytical methods which can be applied to this type of data. Also, easy-to-access tools for interaction, analysis and collaboration during data research and analysis, can support analysis while facilitating knowledge exchange and discussion.

H.7.5 Data publishing and sharing

Case studies illustrate the general trend earlier observed that multidimensional data remain unpublished even though in many instances it has been produced by publicly funded research.

Sharing of data is often limited to outputs such as academic publications and viewing over the web a simplified version, which does not represent or demonstrate the richness of data. Hence, in many cases, the published data outputs do not necessarily represent the wealth or multidimensionality of data (e.g. 2D images instead of 3D models, videos of immersive experiences). For instance, often decimated data are published on Sketchfab for purposes mostly related to audience engagement and education. In fewer cases, researchers put extra effort into publishing data through different platforms; a process which is time-consuming and prone to mistakes.

IPR and content licensing are not always clear when publishing data and the community needs support and clear guidance on how to articulate copyright and assigning licenses to data.

There is a need for publishing solutions which offer feedback mechanisms (e.g. sharing with users/partners within timeframes) and getting feedback for the data.

H.7.6 Data aggregation, use and re-use

Data are often scattered in different repositories and access to data is not always easy. Although there is a desire from the community to aggregate data and make data FAIR compliant, limited data is linked and often the research community does not have specific thoughts on re-use of data.

Appendix I Consortium and Partners

The project consortium has been led by the University of Brighton, and members include:

- Cambridge Digital Humanities
- Duncan of Jordanstone College of Art & Design (DJCAD), University of Dundee
- Historic Environment Scotland
- IIF-3D Community Group
- Kings College London
- Kings Digital Lab
- Mnemoscene
- The British Library
- The National Archives
- The University of Edinburgh
- University College London
- University of Brighton
- The University of the West of England
- Victoria and Albert Museum